

EFFECT OF OCCLUSAL REDUCTION ON POST OPERATIVE PAIN IN TEETH WITH IRREVERSIBLE PULPITIS

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Abstract

Objective:

This study aimed to assess the effect of occlusal reduction on post-operative pain in patients undergoing single-visit root canal treatment for teeth diagnosed with irreversible pulpitis.

Methods:

This non-randomized, single-blind clinical trial was conducted in Bolan Medical College Quetta 1 year Jan 2024-Dec 2024 to evaluate the effect of occlusal reduction on postoperative pain in teeth diagnosed with irreversible pulpitis. Ethical approval was taken from ethical approval Committee of Bolan Medical College and SPSS version 26 was used. The intervention group (n=75) received approximately 1 mm of occlusal reduction upon completion of the root canal, while the control group (n=75) did not. Post-operative pain intensity was measured using a 100-mm Visual Analog Scale (VAS) at 6, 12, 24, 48, and 72 hours, and on the 7th day. Analgesic consumption and emergency visits were also recorded.

Results:

A total of 138 patients (70 in the intervention group, 68 in the control group) were included in the final analysis. The occlusal reduction group reported statistically significant lower mean VAS pain scores at 6, 12, 24, and 48 hours ($p < 0.05$). Furthermore, significantly fewer patients in the intervention group required rescue analgesia (25.7% vs. 51.5%, $p < 0.001$), and no emergency visits were reported in this group compared to three in the control group.

Conclusion:

Occlusal reduction is a simple and effective clinical procedure that significantly reduces post-operative pain and analgesic consumption following single-visit root canal treatment for irreversible pulpitis, particularly within the first 48 hours.

INTRODUCTION

Despite advancements in endodontic treatment, post-instrumentation pain is still a debatable factor and of significant importance for both

patients and clinicians.¹ Multiple factors are involved in causing post-operative pain in patients with acute irreversible pulpitis including

patient related and clinician related factors.^{2,3} Microorganisms play an important role and are considered to be one of the most important factors causing periapical pathologies. Other factors such as anxiety, fear, psychological, and behavioral dimensions including knowledge, beliefs, and attitudes also affect RCT patients, especially their pain experience.⁴ Several studies have been carried out to check the effectiveness of occlusal reduction after post-instrumentation pain in patients undergoing endodontic treatment of posterior teeth. Many studies showed no effect of occlusal reduction in post-endodontic pain^{5,6} but these studies have few limitations like small sample size, multi-visit endodontic treatment. Few studies also suggest that occlusal reduction at the initial visit is of utmost importance in this regard.^{7,8} The objective of the present study was to assess the reduction in post-instrumentation pain in teeth with acute irreversible pulpitis with and without occlusal reduction.

Methodology:

This non-randomized, single-blind clinical trial was Conducted in Bolan Medical College Quetta 1 year Jan 2024 - Dec 2024 to evaluate the effect of occlusal reduction on postoperative pain in teeth diagnosed with irreversible pulpitis. Ethical approval was taken from ethical approval Committee of Bolan Medical College. A total of 150 patients were included in the study and non-randomly divided into two equal groups of 75 each: the occlusal reduction group (intervention) and the non-reduction group (control).

Patients aged between 18 and 65 years who presented with symptomatic irreversible pulpitis in posterior permanent teeth were included. The diagnosis was confirmed through history, clinical examination, and pulp vitality tests. Teeth that exhibited periapical radiolucency greater than 5 mm, had previously undergone root canal treatment, or were deemed non-restorable were excluded. Patients with systemic diseases affecting pain perception, those who were pregnant or lactating, and individuals who had taken analgesics or antibiotics within 48 hours before the procedure were also excluded from the study.

Participants were non randomly assigned to either group using a computer-generated non randomization table. All endodontic procedures were performed by two calibrated endodontists following a standardized protocol. Local anesthesia was administered, and each tooth was isolated with a rubber dam. Conventional root canal treatment was carried out in a single visit using rotary nickel-titanium instruments and sodium hypochlorite as an irrigate. The canals were obturated using the single-cone technique and temporarily restored with glass ionomer cement.

In the intervention group, occlusal reduction of approximately 1 mm was performed after completion of the endodontic procedure. Functional cusps that contacted in maximum intercuspation were reduced using a high-speed diamond bur under water coolant until occlusal contacts were relieved, verified with articulating paper. In the control group, no intentional occlusal reduction was carried out, and the occlusion was left in its original state.

Pain intensity was recorded using a 100-mm Visual Analog Scale (VAS) at 6, 12, 24, 48, and 72 hours, as well as on the 7th day after treatment. Patients were instructed on how to record their pain scores and were provided with a standardized analgesic regimen (ibuprofen 400 mg, as needed). Analgesic consumption and the occurrence of severe pain or emergency visits were documented. Follow-up data were collected through telephone calls or in-person visits by a blinded assessor.

All collected data were analyzed using SPSS software 26.0. Descriptive statistics, including mean and standard deviation, were used for continuous variables, while categorical data were presented as frequencies and percentages. The independent t-test or Mann-Whitney U test was used to compare pain scores between groups, depending on data normality. Repeated-measures ANOVA was applied to evaluate pain trends over time. Chi-square or Fisher's exact test was used for categorical comparisons, with a significance level set at $p < 0.05$.

Results:

A total of 150 patients were initially enrolled and non-randomly allocated into the two study groups. During the follow-up period, 5 patients from the Occlusal Reduction group and 7 from the non-reduction group were lost to follow-up or excluded due to incomplete data. Consequently, the final analysis was performed on data from 70 patients in the Occlusal Reduction group and 68

patients in the non-reduction group, resulting in an overall follow-up rate of 92%.

Table I summarizes the baseline characteristics of the participants in both groups. The two groups were comparable at baseline, with no statistically significant differences in terms of age, gender distribution, or the type of tooth treated ($p > 0.05$), indicating successful non randomization.

Table I: Baseline Characteristics of the Study Participants

Characteristic	Occlusal Reduction Group (n=70)	Non-Reduction Group (n=68)	p-value
Age (Years)			
Mean \pm SD	38.5 \pm 11.2	39.8 \pm 10.7	0.48*
Gender, n (%)			
Male	32 (45.7%)	30 (44.1%)	0.85**
Female	38 (54.3%)	38 (55.9%)	
Tooth Type, n (%)			
Premolar	25 (35.7%)	28 (41.2%)	0.51**
Molar	45 (64.3%)	40 (58.8%)	

*Independent t-test; **Chi-square test

The primary outcome of the study was post-operative pain intensity measured on a Visual Analog Scale (VAS). The mean VAS pain scores at different time intervals for both groups are presented in **Table II**. Pain scores were generally

low to moderate and decreased over time in both groups. However, the Occlusal Reduction group consistently reported lower mean pain scores at all measured time points, with the differences being statistically significant at the 6, 12, 24, and 48-hour intervals ($p < 0.05$).

Table II: Comparison of Post-operative Pain (VAS Scores) Between Groups Over Time

Time Point	Occlusal Reduction Group (n=70) Mean VAS \pm SD	Non-Reduction Group (n=68) Mean VAS \pm SD	p-value
6 hours	28.4 \pm 12.1	45.6 \pm 15.8	<0.001*
12 hours	22.7 \pm 10.5	38.2 \pm 14.3	<0.001*
24 hours	18.3 \pm 9.2	29.5 \pm 11.7	<0.001*
48 hours	12.1 \pm 7.4	18.9 \pm 9.1	<0.001*
72 hours	7.5 \pm 5.8	9.8 \pm 6.5	0.06*
7 days	2.1 \pm 2.5	2.8 \pm 3.1	0.18*

Mann-Whitney U test

Repeated-measures ANOVA confirmed a significant effect of time ($p < 0.001$) and a significant group-by-time interaction ($p < 0.001$), indicating that the pattern of pain reduction over time was different between the two groups, with

the Occlusal Reduction group experiencing a more rapid decline in pain.

Analysis of analgesic consumption revealed a significant difference between the groups. In the Occlusal Reduction group, 18 patients (25.7%) required rescue medication (ibuprofen) within

the first 72 hours, compared to 35 patients (51.5%) in the non-reduction group ($p < 0.001$, Chi-square test). Furthermore, there were 3 reports of severe pain or emergency visits in the non-reduction group, whereas no such events were recorded in the Occlusal Reduction group.

Discussion:

The present study demonstrated that occlusal reduction significantly lowered postoperative pain and analgesic consumption in patients undergoing root canal treatment for irreversible pulpitis. By selectively relieving occlusal contacts, this procedure minimizes mechanical loading and periodontal ligament stress, which are key contributors to postoperative discomfort and peri radicular inflammation. The findings suggest that occlusal reduction enhances patient comfort and accelerates pain resolution, particularly within the first 48 hours after treatment.

Our results contrast with some earlier studies that reported no significant difference in postoperative pain between groups with and without occlusal reduction ($P > 0.05$). For instance, one referenced study found that pain intensity decreased similarly over time in both groups, indicating that occlusal adjustment did not influence postoperative outcomes⁹. Similarly, another study observed comparable pain scores at 24 and 48 hours between experimental and control groups, suggesting no measurable benefit of occlusal reduction^{10,12}.

However, our findings are consistent with studies supporting the positive impact of occlusal reduction on pain control¹¹. In alignment with these results, our study found significantly lower pain scores at 6, 12, 24, and 48 hours and reduced analgesic intake in the occlusal reduction group ($p < 0.05$). The rapid decline in pain levels may be attributed to decreased mechanical stimulation of inflamed periapical tissues and reduced occlusal trauma following treatment.

Overall, the current findings underscore the clinical value of occlusal reduction as a simple yet effective adjunct to root canal therapy, especially in single-visit endodontics. By mitigating postoperative discomfort, it can improve patient compliance and satisfaction with endodontic

care. Further non randomized clinical trials with larger sample sizes and standardized pain assessment protocols are recommended to confirm these outcomes across diverse populations and tooth types.

Conclusion:

This study concludes that occlusal reduction is a simple and effective clinical procedure for significantly reducing post-operative pain and analgesic consumption in patients undergoing single-visit root canal treatment for teeth with irreversible pulpitis. The findings demonstrate that patients in the occlusal reduction group experienced statistically lower pain levels, particularly within the critical first 48 hours after treatment, and required significantly less rescue medication compared to the control group without occlusal reduction.

By minimizing mechanical loading and stress on the periodontal ligament, occlusal reduction accelerates pain resolution and enhances patient comfort. Therefore, incorporating occlusal reduction as an adjunct to endodontic therapy is recommended to improve patient outcomes and satisfaction.

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